

Enhanced food security under global change requires a tritrophic perspective

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Keywords: invasive species, pest risk analysis, time-varying life tables, population dynamics, agroecology.

Introduction

Global change is altering the relationships between crops, pests, and natural enemies, and accelerating the spread of destructive invasive species. These changes pose a significant threat to agricultural production and food security worldwide (Cuthbert et al., 2022). Current risk assessment strategies often rely on correlative species distribution models (CSDMs) that lack the capacity to predict the complex, weather-driven population dynamics essential for informing robust management and policy development. To bridge this gap, a mechanistic framework using physiologically based demographic models (PBDMs) was proposed (Gutierrez and Baumgärtner, 1984). This framework posits that by capturing the fundamental, weather-driven biology of resource acquisition and allocation at each trophic level, we can develop powerful, predictive models of crop systems that are independent of time and place, providing a sound basis for proactive crop management. A web platform is proposed to assist non-experts in formulating PBDMs to help solve agroecological pest problems (Gutierrez et al., 2025).

Materials and Methods

To outline the development and demonstrate the utility of this framework as web platform software for non-experts, we utilize PBDMs for 13 invasive pest species of agroecological importance to Africa to predict their geographic distribution, relative abundance, and dynamics across the continent. The PBDM framework is based on the paradigm of time-varying life tables (TVLTs) (Gutierrez and Baumgärtner, 1984), which mathematically describes by analogy the developmental biology of all multicellular organisms (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Analogous developmental stages of a plant and an insect, with the bottom panel characterizing survivorship (l_x) and reproductive profiles (m_x). Note that the developmental times of individuals initiated at the same time have distributed developmental rates (Gutierrez et al., 2025).

The models for all trophic levels are age-structured and parameterized using two related approaches: (1) a metabolic pool (MP) approach for resource acquisition and allocation, or (2) biodemographic functions (BDFs) fitted to vital rates (e.g., development, mortality, reproduction) from life-table studies (Gutierrez and Baumgärtner, 1984). By analogy, this unified structure allows the same modeling principles to be applied across taxonomically diverse species. A common

Crop Modelling
for Agriculture
and Food Security
under Global Change

February 2 - 4 2026
Palazzo dei Congressi
Florence, Italy

modeling framework was employed to develop PBDMs for 13 invasive species systems of major agroecological importance to Africa, encompassing a total of 20 species, including crops, pests, natural enemies, diseases, vectors, and parasites. The underlying precepts of the approach are based on 1960-1970s crop plant modeling concepts of C.T. de Wit summarized for the WOFOST crop simulation model by A. de Wit et al. (2019).

Results and Discussion

In a GIS context, the PBDM framework successfully simulated the prospective geographic distribution and relative abundance of all 13 invasive species across Africa (Gutierrez et al., 2025). By focusing on the species' physiological responses to local weather, the models provided dynamic predictions that compared favorably to published data.

For example, the invasive pest South American tomato pinworm (*Tuta absoluta*), originally from Peru's cool highlands, spread to subtropical Brazil and was first detected in Europe (Spain) in 2006. Early assessments in 2010 and 2019 incorrectly predicted the pest would only survive in coastal southern Europe, due to its warm-climate expansion in South America. However, these predictions failed because researchers overlooked the pest's origins in the cold, semi-arid Andean highlands, which enabled it to survive in much broader climatic conditions. As a result, *T. absoluta* colonized far more of Europe than expected. By the time scientists recognized its full invasive potential, it had spread across large areas of Europe, with subsequent invasion of Africa and parts of Asia, where it poses a significant threat to food security. The prospective invasive distribution of *T. absoluta* in Africa includes the cooler climes of Senegal and Morocco, across coastal North Africa to Egypt and the Levant, with the highest populations found in sub-tropical and tropical Africa and decreasing levels in temperate regions of South Africa.

In contrast, PBDM analysis predicts that the highly destructive polyphagous pest Asian brown marmorated stink bug (*Halyomorpha halys*) would find most of sub-Saharan Africa unfavorable, with suitable niches restricted to coastal North Africa and the tip of South Africa. This analysis contradicts predictions from CSDM algorithms, including CLIMEX, which project a wide potential distribution in the region.

The PBDM framework routinely handled agroecological complexity that is intractable with CSDMs, including tritrophic daily dynamics of and interactions between the citrus crop, its pest *Diaphorina citri*, the natural enemy *Tamarixia radiata*, and the bacterial pathogen that causes citrus greening disease and is vectored by the pest. These and other examples highlight the critical importance of incorporating mechanistic biology to avoid potentially misleading risk assessments and more effectively target management strategies in cropping systems.

Conclusions

PBDMs provide a robust, mechanistic alternative to correlative methods for assessing the dynamics, distribution, and abundance of native and invasive pests interacting with their host crops under global change. In a multitrophic context, they hold high potential for examining the complex agroecology at the heart of crop production, integrated pest management, and biological control (see Tixier et al., 2013). By grounding predictions about the dynamics in the fundamental biology of the organisms, PBDMs deliver more reliable insights to safeguard food security. As with major cropping systems models, such as WOFOST (de Wit et al., 2019), which focus on crop growth and development, we advocate for the development of a web-based platform to make tritrophic demographic modeling approaches more accessible to non-experts, thereby fostering a global, proactive, and science-based pest management approach.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by CASAS Global NGO, the McKnight Foundation (grant numbers 22-341 and 24-124), and project TEBAKA (project ID: ARS01_00815) co-funded by the European Union.

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